

The basic characteristic of life

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Abstract: Life doesn't seem like just a simple amalgamation of chemical substances in various states of aggregation, and thus, in order to successfully program a computer simulation for a simple form of life, it will be necessary to identify the fundamental characteristics of life. Current observations based on theories of adaptation to the external environment should be revisited, and a new characteristic, one that has been overlooked, might need to be identified—perhaps because it is so obvious. The basic function of life is the transformation of the environment, of the entire natural world surrounding it, but not in its substance, rather in an intelligible symbol that will be a component part of another new individual symbolic world. And when I say symbol, I refer to a kind of synthesis of something, a systematized utility for to be used. This other world of otherness will include at least a necessary functional component, and much more. The attempt to establish a new world through neural networks is the justification of life.

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Computerized simulation of life

There are some notable attempts to simulate life on computers, especially within the fields of artificial life and computational biology. Some of these efforts aim to replicate the processes of life, such as self-replication, evolution, and adaptation.

One major development has been in computer simulations of the origin of life, where researchers use models to explore how life might have started from simple chemical reactions. The journal *Life* has published a special issue on this topic, focusing on evolutionary dynamics and the role of computer simulation in understanding the origin of life, with a particular emphasis on the RNA world hypothesis and prebiotic chemistry. These models are often used methods to simulate the complex interactions that could have led to the first living organisms.

A study in this special issue of *Life* argues that it would be beneficial to further explore the stabilization and functionalization mechanisms of protocells within the Earth's crust. (Dávila 2023). Another study, based on the idea of an RNA world, demonstrates that the concept of order and complexity is a versatile and powerful tool for evaluating the efficiency of general evolutionary processes. (Mayer 2023). Shi, Y. puts forward an intriguing idea, the Direct RNA Template (DRT) hypothesis, which suggests that RNA molecules can directly bind specific amino acids and facilitate the synthesis of corresponding peptides, thus initiating the RNA/peptides world (Shi 2023). Another study showed that [GADV] peptides, which form secondary structures, have low water solubility. [GADVE] peptides were preferred for presumed primitive proteins (Kato 2023). The work of Kua and Miller provides a foundational free energy map for potential CHOS metabolites in the core, and future research will extend this map to encompass nitrogen-containing compounds like amino acids, pterins, pyrroles, and pyrimidines, which may be involved in broader intermediary metabolism. Then these compounds are also anticipated to function as

primitive catalysts and cofactors in the establishment of proto-metabolic cycles (Kua 2022).

The idea that chemical evolution led to the origin of life still leaves open the question of exactly how it could have led to a coherent and self-reproducing collective of molecules. Hordijk and colleagues suggest that one possible answer to this question was proposed in the form of the emergence of an autocatalytic set: a collection of molecules that mutually catalyze each other's formation and that is self-sustaining given some basic "food" source. They investigate in more detail when and how autocatalytic sets can arise in a simple model of chemical evolution based on the idea of combinatorial innovation with random catalysis assignments. They derive theoretical results, compare them with computer simulations, and suggest that these results could point to a possible step towards the (or an) origin of life (Hordijk 2022). Then, the rolling circle mechanism found in viroids and some RNA viruses, as proposed by Rivera-Madrinan and colleagues, is a likely way that replication could have begun in the RNA World (Rivera-Madrinan 2022).

Roy and Sengupta argue that the hot spring hypothesis of the origin of life offers an interesting test bed for studying evolutionary processes and evaluating the viability of these processes in supporting the formation, growth, division, and eventual proliferation of protocells with increasing functional complexity (Roy 2022).

In a proposed article for publication in Cornell University's *Neural and Evolutionary Computing*, and revised on August 2, 2024, in the field of computational life studies, researchers have developed simple computational substrates that mimic the behavior of self-replicating systems. The study explored how different programming languages and machine instruction sets could simulate life-like processes, such as replication and mutation. These simulations help to provide insights into the theoretical aspects of biological life, such as how self-replicating

structures could emerge and evolve in a computational environment. (Agüera y Arcas 2024).

Moreover, the potential of quantum computing is being explored to simulate evolutionary processes on a molecular level, allowing for more complex and accurate models that could potentially reflect the actual quantum mechanics at play in biological systems. These ongoing studies show that while we are far from fully simulating life as we know it, computational models provide a powerful tool for studying the principles of life and evolution. The starting point would be to identify a clear description of life using a minimum set of criteria. New ideas for the definition of life underline the extreme difficulty in reaching a consensus on this issue. Different theories assign varying importance to the phenomena associated with living systems. (id. Agüera y Arcas).

Jaime Gómez-Márquez, in his attempt to define what life is—likely driven by the legitimate hope that it can be found elsewhere in the universe beyond Earth—concludes that it is a process that takes place in highly organized organic structures and is characterized by being preprogrammed, interactive, adaptive, and evolutionary (Gómez-Márquez 2021).

It would be too simplistic to view life as merely an amalgam of chemicals subjected to various temperatures and external conditions, a product of chance. Instead, it seems more like the end result of something that signifies a new beginning. I say this because the characteristics of life, found in both the simplest and most complex beings, appear to share a common foundation at a basic level. Thus, the first form of life seems to have already existed on the blueprint of an architect.

A simplification of the function of life to highlight its basic characteristics

For a study on the possibility of computer-simulating life, we should focus on the main characteristics of life as they are currently observed and then on L.U.C.A. (Last Universal Common Ancestor) as the simplest, albeit hypothetical, form of life. To begin, I needed to examine the characteristics of life to establish the foundations for future computational coding.

When setting out on a journey, you need to have an idea of the direction you're heading; otherwise, you'll end up nowhere—or at least, that's how a serious traveler would approach it, someone who understands they need to reach a destination. Now, the great journey I'm about to discuss below is the journey of life on Earth. That is, we've arrived somewhere, where we can somewhat observe what this life is—a life we are so proud to share. Yet, we still don't know where it's headed, and if we don't know that, it's clear we currently know very little about it.

So, where is life headed, if it's heading anywhere at all? Toward a final evolution? Or toward an endless, perpetual evolution? And if it is evolving, what would its ultimate destination look like? If we discover this, we might be able to understand more about life in general and about ourselves in particular, to better grasp what we should be doing—and more importantly, what is necessary to do. Let us embark on this journey, just as many before us have. At least we know they didn't get too far. Let's approach it as Jacob Bronowski (1973) suggested when he said: "This is the essence of science: ask an impertinent question, and you are on the way to a pertinent answer." This is my impertinent question: "Where is life headed?"

Life has fundamental characteristics that distinguish living beings from non-living matter. These traits are essential for all living organisms, from the simplest bacteria to complex forms of life such as plants, animals, and humans. The most important characteristics of life are: highly

organized, preprogrammed , interactive , adaptive , and evolutionary provides a nuanced understanding of what life entails. (id. Gómez-Márquez). I am now making a developmental science of these characteristics according to common knowledge.

Highly Organized Organic Structures. Life exists within complex, structured systems built from organic molecules like proteins, lipids, carbohydrates, and nucleic acids. Life is not random; it follows precise arrangements, from the cellular level to the organization of tissues, organs, and ecosystems. Cellular organization is fundamental: from prokaryotic cells (bacteria, archaea) to highly specialized eukaryotic cells (plants, animals). DNA and RNA are organized information storage molecules that guide cellular processes. Membranes, organelles, and multicellular structures create environments for specialized functions.

Preprogrammed. Life operates based on genetic instructions encoded in DNA or RNA. Genetic material acts as a "program" containing instructions for growth, reproduction, repair, and metabolic processes. Preprogrammed mechanisms allow life to maintain homeostasis and reproduce consistently across generations. Embryonic development follows genetic instructions to form complex organisms. Bacterial replication adheres to specific sequences encoded in their genetic material.

Interactive. Life continuously interacts with its environment to obtain energy, nutrients, and information for survival and even more than that. Organisms sense and respond to external stimuli (e.g., light, temperature, chemicals). Interaction can be passive (adaptations) or active (movement, communication). Plants grow towards light (phototropism). Animals migrate or change behavior in response to seasonal changes.

Adaptive. Life adjusts to environmental changes, ensuring survival and reproduction. Adaptation can occur within a single organism's lifetime (phenotypic plasticity) or across generations (evolution). Homeostasis enables organisms to stabilize internal conditions despite external

fluctuations. Polar bears develop thick fur for Arctic conditions. Bacteria evolve resistance to antibiotics through rapid genetic changes.

Evolutionary. Life evolves through natural selection, resulting in changes in populations over generations. Mutations and genetic recombination introduce variation, which natural selection acts upon. Over time, beneficial traits become more common, while less advantageous traits diminish. Darwin's finches evolved beak shapes to exploit different food sources. Microorganisms adapt to new environments, such as extremophiles thriving in volcanic vents.

Integrating those characteristics, life, defined through these attributes, is a dynamic process rather than a static state. A living system:

1. Organizes itself through intricate molecular and cellular structures.
2. Carries pre-programmed instructions in its genetic code to regulate activities and propagate itself.
3. Interacts with its environment, ensuring its survival and reproduction.
4. Adapts to changes in real time and across evolutionary timescales.
5. Evolves, refining its traits to better suit its surroundings over generations.

These characteristics suggest that life is not confined to Earth. If we discover structures elsewhere that exhibit these traits (e.g., organized molecular systems with adaptive and evolutionary behavior), they may qualify as life, even if they differ from terrestrial biology. These characteristics would highlight the uniqueness of life and its complexity, demonstrating how all organisms are connected through certain fundamental common traits.

About the hypothetical L.U.C.A. (Last Universal Common Ancestor)

If we focus on the issue of definition and wish to identify the simplest form of life, we should do so in the simplest possible way—by placing under the philosopher's microscope the simplest form of life, one so simple that we might not even observe it, so to speak. One that exists on the edge of life, but also an imaginary one, where the characteristics of life would be functional, and this functionality is possible through the use of environmental resources. But perhaps this is the basic function of life: this use of environmental resources, this appropriation of the natural world that surrounds it. Not for consumption, as the destruction of the consumed substance, but for the assimilation of another, for the assimilation of everything else, to ultimately make possible, through evolution's end, a new world—one as full of life as the last.

There is a sharp divide in the organizational complexity of the cell between eukaryotes, which have complex intracellular compartmentalization, and even the most sophisticated prokaryotes (archaea and bacteria), which do not. The conservation of the major features of cellular organization and the existence of a large set of genes that are conserved across eukaryotes leave no doubt that all extant eukaryotic forms evolved from a last eukaryote common ancestor (LECA). The reconstruction of other aspects of the genomic composition and architecture of LECA similarly suggests an extremely complex ancestral genome. (KOONIN 2010)

Previously sophisticated eukaryotes, in the very earliest phases of life on Earth, witnessed the origin of life and genetics from the elements. There was a time when there was no life on Earth, and there was a time when there were DNA-inheriting cells. Somewhere on the ocean-covered early Earth and in a narrow window of time of only about 200 million years, the first cells came into existence. Because the genetic code and amino acid chirality are universal, all modern life forms ultimately trace back to that phase of

evolution. That was the time during which the last universal common ancestor (LUCA) of all cells lived. LUCA is a theoretical construct—it might or might not have been something we today would call an organism. It helps to bridge the conceptual gap between rocks and water on the early Earth and ideas about the nature of the first cells. (WEISS 2018)

According to a traditional approach to LUCA has been to simply look for the genes that are present in all genomes. We found a collection of about 30 genes, mostly for ribosomal proteins, telling us that LUCA had a ribosome and had the genetic code (id. WEISS). Ribosomes "read" the genetic code present in mRNA and use it to assemble proteins by linking amino acids in the correct order. This process requires a precise understanding of the codons within the mRNA, which is facilitated by the ribosome's reading frame and the complementary interaction with tRNA molecules that bring amino acids to the ribosome. The ribosome's ability to translate the genetic code into functional proteins is fundamental to all cellular processes and life as a whole.

The genetic code structure refers to the way genetic information in DNA or RNA sequences is translated into proteins. The structure of the genetic code is essential for understanding how sequences of nucleotides (the building blocks of DNA and RNA) are interpreted by cells to produce proteins, which perform virtually all functions necessary for life.

If L.U.C.A. has 30 genes, mostly for ribosomal proteins, telling us that LUCA had a ribosome and had the genetic code. Then this ribosome, which contains the genetic information, is the one that proceeds to modify its environment, and it is there that the emergence of life should be sought. We take one more step and calculate the number of permutations possible for 30 genes of L.U.C.A. to create proteins depending on how you interpret the arrangement and usage of the genes.

The number of possible permutations for 30 genes of L.U.C.A.

Approaching the problem idealized and purely mathematically, although I am not a specialist, if we use genes in a specific sequence without repetition. If the order of genes matters (e.g., gene 1, gene 2, gene 3, ... gene 30), and each gene is used exactly once, the number of permutations is calculated as: $30! = 30 \times 29 \times 28 \times \dots \times 130!$ This is an extremely large number: $30! \approx 2.65 \times 10^{32}!$

If we use genes in combinations (order doesn't matter) and choosing k genes out of 30 (e.g., subsets of genes), and the order does not matter, the number of combinations is:

$$\binom{30}{k} = \frac{30!}{k!(30 - k)!}$$

For example if $k=3$, the number of combinations is:

$$\binom{30}{3} = \frac{30 \times 29 \times 28}{3 \times 2 \times 1} = 4060$$

If the genes can interact in different ways (e.g., forming networks, producing proteins via multiple pathways, or expressing differently under certain conditions), the number of permutations can increase dramatically based on the complexity of interactions. These interactions would need additional biological constraints to calculate. If each gene can be expressed more than once or in multiple ways (e.g., alternative splicing, isoforms), the number of protein combinations would depend on those variations.

If you are asking about all possible orders of the 30 genes, the answer is the factorial $30!$, which is approximately 2.65×10^{32} . However, in biological

systems, constraints like regulatory mechanisms, protein folding, and functional limits greatly reduce the actual number of possible proteins.

A typical human cell uses about 20,000 genes, but the actual number of expressed proteins is estimated at over 100,000–1,000,000, due to alternative splicing and post-translational modifications. For a simpler 30-gene system, the number of biologically meaningful proteins would likely be far fewer than the purely mathematical permutations.

The value of 2.65×10^{32} is 265 followed by 30 zeros in standard notation. If we imagine that a permutation takes place every day, and moreover the result is preserved, so as not to repeat itself, we can identify the period of time required to reach this extremely large value. It would take approx 7.26×10^{29} years to count 2.65×10^{32} numbers, one per day. This is an immeasurably large period, much longer than the age of the Universe (estimated at ~13.8 billion years). What I am suggesting here is a simple matter of mathematics, but perhaps in the evolution of life, we have other forces that should be taken into account.

The basic characteristic of life

Living beings continuously interact with their environment, both affecting it and being influenced by it. These interactions contribute to the natural cycles of the ecosystem through functional reciprocity, which may be the starting point: the creation of otherness as a necessity of life. The cell aspires to become something else—everything it encounters or might encounter. It prepares to internally recompose, not to engulf but to "neuronize." For this, it needs a primary self, which is the otherness of its nearest counterpart.

Interaction with the environment (1) is Motion (2) encompassing through Metabolism (3); motion as a Response to stimuli (4), Adaptation to

them (5) through neural integration, Growth and development (6) as a necessity for optimizing motion, Encompassing genetic information through Metabolism (7), Homeostasis (8) of Biological Organization (9), which is preserved through heredity, and Reproduction (10).

These characteristics highlight the uniqueness and complexity of life, demonstrating how all organisms are interconnected through common fundamental principles. The primary principle is what I call, and hope I am inspired in doing so, Neuronization.

We have two phases:

I. Self-stability for ensuring Neuronation. Homeostasis (7), maintained through the preservation of biological organization (8), is achieved via Reproduction (9), which ensures that genetic information is preserved through heredity (10) as an acceptance of potential failure.

II. Creation of alterity through Neuronation. Metabolism (1) is the primary interaction with the environment (2), but also the ultimate one, Adaptation (3) to it, which, from an observer's perspective, manifests as Movement (4) and Response to stimuli (5), optimized through Growth and development (6).

But the assumption of the potential for failure, necessary for Reproduction, cannot be a characteristic of the architect of life; rather, it must be the protection of life through a continuous flow of reinforcing the environment and the development of life for the potential of otherness. Thus, LUCA did not merely exist; it continues to exist, but it is difficult to observe in the material environment—it is barely perceptible. It is something that, from one perspective, appears non-living, and from another, just barely alive. The mission of otherness is a continuous one, not one that has been completed.

In this sense, L.U.C.A. should not be directly unicellular but rather a cellular potential, an environment only slightly altered, an environment that seems to come alive (through essential characteristics I and then II).

The stability of the self to ensure Neuronation (I) and then the creation of otherness through Neuronation (II). Could LUCA have only I (projection) without II? If it lacks II, can it still be considered life? But the stability of the self to ensure Neuronation (I) implies the potentiality of Neuronation, so it must also have II.

Then, the failure of Neuronation generates reproduction—a copy of the self, a copy of itself. Yes, but at the beginning, I appears as a necessity for II. Therefore, if II fails, it is due to I, and then (I, II, III).

Neuronation. Neuronal refers to something related to neurons, and Neuronation also pertains to neurons, specifically to a particular action they perform—namely, the assimilation of otherness from nature. It is not so much connected to neural imagery, which might only represent a visible part, but rather to the entire activity of the mind—something distinct from the brain itself.

I. The stability of the self to ensure the possibility of Neuronation. Homeostasis (1) for maintaining Biological Organization (2);

II. The creation of otherness through Neuronation. Metabolism (3) is the primary interaction with the environment (4) but also the final one, Adaptation (5) to it, which from the perspective of an observer is Movement (6), a Response to stimuli (7) optimized through Growth and development (8);

III. The multiplication of the self for a new attempt at Neuronation. The restoration of organization is ensured through Reproduction (9), which ensures that Genetic information is preserved through inheritance (10) as the multiplication of the self for a new attempt at Neuronation.

I. It is ensured by the re-submission (preservation) of the LUCA template, regardless of the success of the initial template. Perhaps it

can be corrected after the initial template, which is redesigned, and will then always seek conformity with it. Initial genetic material as objects of unchanged code.

- II. Here, the template must act autonomously to fulfill the meaning of life, creating otherness through Neuronation. Neuronation as all plus me, or me in all, in genetic material as objects of code.
- III. Here, the template reproduces using material from the environment integrated within itself, where it is designed to fulfill the meaning of life, creating otherness through Neuronation. Genetic material as objects of code.

The theory of evolution was established by Charles Darwin in his work *The Origin of Species* (1859), where he introduced the concept of natural selection as the primary mechanism of evolution. According to this theory, organisms that exhibit genetic variations favorable to their environment have a greater chance of survival and reproduction, leading to the transmission of these traits to future generations. This idea was influenced by Darwin's observations of biodiversity in the Galápagos Islands and by the work of economist Thomas Malthus on competition for resources. Charles Darwin introduces the concept of natural selection in Chapter IV of *The Origin of Species* (1859), titled "Natural Selection; or, the Survival of the Fittest," through observations such as: "...every slight modification, which in the course of ages chanced to arise, and which in any way favoured the individuals of any of the species, by better adapting them to their altered conditions, would tend to be preserved; and natural selection would thus have free scope for the work of improvement." (DARWIN p. 82 1859).

Adaptation to the environment does not seem to be the ultimate goal of life. When I say this, I am not necessarily referring to the existence of species in the Phylliidae family (BANK, 2021), insects that provide a classic example of evolutionary adaptation and are intensely studied to understand the mechanisms of mimicry and impressive camouflage that allow them to

evade predators by perfectly mimicking the leaves in their environment, or to anything else that stands out based on these criteria; but rather to anything related to this evolutionary adaptation, including the Phylliidae family. There are flowers that mimic insects to attract pollinators, and some of them have extremely complex structures that appear to outline anatomical details of insects. Orchids in the genus *Ophrys* are known for sexual mimicry, imitating the shape, color, and texture of female bodies of certain insects, especially bees or wasps. Then there are carnivorous plants (e.g., *Nepenthes* or *Sarracenia*) that do not explicitly mimic the internal organs of insects, but in the case of certain carnivorous species, such as *Nepenthes*, the inside of the trap may vaguely resemble internal structures (e.g., an esophagus or stomach). The plants described above provide extraordinary examples of coevolution with insects. They use their mimicry to maximize their chances of pollination or to capture prey. These mechanisms are observed as fascinating examples of evolutionary adaptations, but they seem statistically improbable, and I will not insist on making this mathematical demonstration so as not to digress from the subject. The animals and plants mentioned as examples, however, seem to do more than simply adapt to their natural environment; they seem to have, in some way, a relationship with their environment, a reciprocal relationship—not just their action on the environment, but also the environment's action on them. Not only their adaptation to the environment but also their taking in of their environment. A taking in of the entire environment perceptible to them, and a transformation of this taking in by creating an alterity of this acquired, but to better fix the idea, we must go through a brief biography.

Several scientific discoveries demonstrate the flexibility and relevance of Darwin's theory in light of new technologies and data. The general statistical model shows that macroevolutionary models and processes align with Darwinian gradualism, even though species phenotypes frequently change abruptly or experience long periods of

stasis—both of which contradict the theory of incremental change or gradualism (PAGEL 2022).

According to Lysenko 1953 a Ukrainian agronomist researcher, a living body consists of elements from the external environment that it has assimilated through metabolism: "*The modification of the nature of a living body is due to the modification of the type of assimilation, the modification of the type of metabolism. Once external conditions are absorbed and assimilated by the living body, they are no longer external conditions but internal ones; in other words, they become elements of the living body and require food, external environmental conditions for growth and development—conditions that were once external but have now become part of the living body. In a sense, the living body is made up of elements from the external environment that it has assimilated.*" (PIAGET, CHOMSKY 167, 1988).

It is evident that there is some connection between the living body and its environment, and adaptation to environmental conditions involves an evolutionary modification of the living body. From this perspective, there is an internalization of external conditions through substance exchanges, mainly as a result of metabolism. However, this evolution does not follow the classical path of adaptation, of establishing a living body optimized for environmental conditions. Rather, it is about the adaptation of the compound between the environment and the living organisms that inhabit it, within the conditions of the living organism. The issue is not about altering the environment, but rather about creating an otherness to the environment—a new environment more optimal for the living body, a new environment based on an internally projected dimension and neuronally supported. Evolution would then be observed as a kind of devolution, a transmission of everything towards a new standard, a progress of everything, a potential universal otherness.

This internalization of external conditions through metabolism I call alterity, meaning the ability of the living body to assimilate the natural world around it, but not necessarily by consuming its substance. The

process of this assimilation I call neuronization, or the transposition of the natural world into a neural map, into the supernatural, into the invisible as the alterity of the world, into a new world contained within the mind and supported by various neural structures. The transposed natural world continues, in a way, to interact in this invisibility within us, and this interaction is possible only if this transposition consists of somewhat independent mental objects. I do not believe that this entire world of alterity is as complex as the natural world it transposes into the supernatural, but it is complex enough to allow its functional establishment. The decryption code of the neural maps and the interactions between the mental objects is indecipherable, being a temporal individual construct, a specificity of each individual, of each living entity. Although indecipherable, the simulation of a reconstruction of the neuronal universe seems to be partially possible, as long as we identify the relevant mental objects contained within it and find a way to define them according to their possessor, according to the connection formed between them in the mind. This is the answer to one of the great questions of life: the fact that every time we face a living body, we face an entire universe on its way to becoming.

This seems to be the basic function of life: a transformation of the environment, of the entire natural world surrounding it, but not in its substance, rather in an intelligible symbol that will be a component part of another new symbolic world. And when I say symbol, I refer to a kind of synthesis of something, a systematized utility for it to be used. This other world of otherness will include at least a necessary functional component, and much more. The attempt to establish a new world through neural networks is the justification of life.

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